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A STUDY ON CHALLENGES OF CUSTOMERS WITH ATM SERVICES

Smt. B. Venkata Lakshmi1,
Assistant Professor,

Department of Humanities & Sciences (Management),
KSRM College of Engineering (Autonomous), YSR Kadapa-516005, Andhra Pradesh,
India,
e-mail: lakshmireddy.sl@gmail.com

Mr. Muneiah Tellakula,
Assistant Professor,

Department of CSE Cyber Security (CS),
Rajeev Gandhi Memorial College of Engineering and Technology (Autonomous),
Nandyala, Andhra Pradesh, Pin Code-518501, India, Email:
muneiahtellakula@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Automated Teller Machines (ATMs) are the first remarkable machines to provide electronic access to bank customers. They offer multiple advantages such as cash withdrawal, cash deposit, and balance enquiry. With ATMs, bankers have the ability to serve their customers even outside the bank premises. The main objective of this study is to identify the challenges faced by customers in using ATM services. The data was collected from both primary and secondary sources. The primary data was obtained through a Google Form questionnaire with 302 sample respondents, while the secondary data was collected from publications and websites. The sample respondents in this study were ATM card holders, selected on the basis of convenient sampling. The findings reveal that the major challenges associated with ATMs

include waiting in queues at ATM centers, machines being out of service, shortage of cash, and non-printing of transaction slips

Keywords: Automatic Teller Machine (ATM), Banking Services, Customer Satisfaction, and Challenges.

INTRODUCTION

As technology rapidly spreads across India, online banking is increasingly becoming a common method of conducting financial transactions. In this context, bankers in India need to make greater efforts to sustain and retain their customers by delivering better services. Technological advancement has played an important role in improving service delivery standards in the Indian banking industry. The Automated Teller Machine (ATM) card is a plastic card embedded with a magnetic chip that allows customers to be identified through their

Personal Identification Number (PIN). This innovation has provided both customers and banks with an enhanced experience by reducing disruptions in traditional banking operations. ATMs are among the first remarkable machines that offered electronic access to bank services. There are multiple advantages of ATMs, such as cash withdrawal, cash deposit, and balance inquiry. With ATMs, banks are able to serve their customers beyond branch premises. People of different age groups have varying needs, and ATMs are used for diverse purposes accordingly. ATMs are considered a technological advancement of the Core Banking System (CBS), which was readily adopted by banks. CBS encompasses the implementation of electronic payment methods such as ATM services, mobile banking, and digital banking. Within this system, ATM services operate through unique PINs and provide customers with convenience, accessibility, and efficiency

LITERATURE REVIEW

Nyi Lwin (2019) in this study "The impact of ATM Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction in the Private Commercial Banking Industry in Yangon, Myanmar" analyzed the customer satisfaction on Automated Teller Machines (ATM) in Private Commercial Banks of Yangon city. The study found that majority of the respondents in each the banks upset with the ATM grievance settlement. The authors suggested that banks improve their performance, supply the safety measures and provide new cards for rapidly if the card is missed by the customers. The study concluded that bankers are need to increase awareness to their customers about ATM, Debit Cards and Credit cards. The study recommended that bankers develop proper

mechanism to resolve the complaints, it leads to customer satisfaction and arrange the ATMs at all the useful places like malls, hospitals and buying malls etc.

Ikechi, A, Robinson, J.C, & Emelike, N.O. (2018) in this study "ATM Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction: A Study of First Bank of Nigeria Plc and Union Bank of Nigeria Plc" examine the relationship between ATM service quality and customer satisfaction. The authors found that null hypotheses one to six which postulate that there is no significant correlation between each of the six independent variables (Reliability, Assurance, Tangibles, Empathy, Responsiveness and Cost). The study concluded that banks should work on building confidence in their customers if they want the referrals of customers to improve significantly.

Eugene Oware Koranteng and Evans Brako Ntiamoah et. All. (2016) in their study "A Theoretical Analysis of Automated Teller Machine (ATM) System on Customer Satisfaction in the Banking Industry: The Case Study of HFC Bank" identified the impact of ATMs on customer satisfaction. The study found that customers were dissatisfied with the maximum amount one can withdraw with the one card is not enough. The authors suggested that the bankers should increase the maximum number of withdraws and educate the customers on the usage of the ATMs.

R. Renuka and A. Paulraj (2014) in this study "Customers' Satisfaction Towards Automated Teller Machine, Indian Journal of Applied Research" analyzed the customer satisfaction towards ATM services offered by the banks. The author

found that majority of the respondents were aware about the features and satisfied with the 24-Hours access. In this study most of the respondents are using ATM services twice in a month and used for cash withdrawal and balance enquiry. The authors suggested that Banks should provide awareness about various facilities offered by ATM then only people can know about different features and also limit in with cash per day may be increased. The study concluded that need to improve the safety and security in ATM services and also banks should frequently inspect the ATMs, it is helpful to avoid breakdown of ATMs.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

- To find out the challenges of customers with Automatic Teller Machines (ATM) services.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The main objective of the study is to find out the challenges of customers with ATM services. The data was collected from both primary and secondary sources. The primary data was collected through google form questionnaire with 302 sample respondents. The secondary data has collected through publications and websites. The sample respondents to be used in this study are ATM card holders. In this study customers were selected on the basis of convenient sampling.

Figure -1

How satisfied are you with the overall ATM services provided by your bank?
302 responses

Source: Primary data.

It is observed from the above figure majority respondents are satisfied with the Automatic Teller Machine services provided by the Bankers and some of the respondents are neutral satisfied with the ATM services. Only few respondents are dissatisfied with the Automatic Teller Machine services.

Figure-2

What are the challenges, if any, have you faced while using ATM
302 responses

Source: Primary data.

It is understood from the analysis of the above figure among the total 41.1 per cent of the respondents are facing challenges regarding additional charges on after limited withdrawals and remaining respondents are facing challenges regarding lack of ATMs in rural areas, out-of-service Automatic Teller Machines, difficulty in understanding Automatic Teller Machine operations and privacy-related concerns. Customers convenient is the location of the ATM shown in the following figure.

Figure -3

How convenient is the location of the nearest ATM to your home or workplace?
302 responses

Source: Primary data.

It is observed from the above figure majority Automatic Teller Machine users are feel convenient with the location of the Automatic Teller Machines and some of the Automatic Teller Machine users are feel neutral with the location of the ATM Machines. Only few Automatic Teller Machine users are feel inconvenient with the location of ATM Machines.

Figure-4

How secure do you feel when using an ATM?
302 responses

Source: Primary data.

The table exhibits that majority sample respondents are feel secure when using an Automatic Teller Machine services and some of the Automatic Teller Machine users are feel insecure when using an ATM Card service.

Figure -5

What improvements would you like to see in ATM services?
302 responses

Source: Primary data.

The above figure exhibits that majority sample respondents are opened that need to establish more Automatic Teller Machines at rural areas with better functionality. Some of the Automatic Teller Machine users suggested enhanced security measures, need to reduced transaction fees and provide fast customer services.

Figure-6

Would you recommend your bank's ATM services to others?
302 responses

Source: Primary data.

The above figure exhibits the opinion of Automatic Teller Machines users regarding ATM services recommend to the others. The table exhibits that majority sample respondents are ready to recommend Automatic Teller Machines services to the others and some of the Automatic Teller Machine users are probably recommend Automatic Teller Machines services to the others. Only few respondents are not recommended Automatic Teller Machines to the others.

Figure-7

What is your opinion about Limitations of ATM Service
302 responses

Source: Primary data.

It is understood from the analysis of the above figure among the total 51.3 per cent opinion of the respondents are satisfied with the limitations of Automatic Teller Machines and some of the Automatic Teller Machines users are moderately satisfied with the limitations of ATM Card services. Only few respondents are dissatisfied with the limitations of Automatic Teller Machines.

FINDINGS AND SUGGESTIONS

1. Majority respondents are satisfied with the Automatic Teller Machine services provided by the Bankers and some of the respondents are neutral satisfied with the ATM services. Only few respondents are dissatisfied with the Automatic Teller Machine services.
2. Among the total sample respondents most of the respondents are facing challenges regarding additional charges on after limited withdrawals and remaining respondents are facing challenges regarding lack of ATMs in rural areas, out-of-service Automatic Teller Machines, difficulty in understanding Automatic Teller Machine operations and privacy-related concerns.
3. Majority Automatic Teller Machine users are feeling convenient with the location of the Automatic Teller Machines and some of the Automatic Teller Machine users are feel neutral

with the location of the ATM Machines. Only few Automatic Teller Machine users are feel inconvenient with the location of ATM Machines.

4. Majority sample respondents are ready to recommend Automatic Teller Machines services to the others and some of the Automatic Teller Machine users are probably recommend Automatic Teller Machines services to the others.
5. Among the total 51.3 per cent opinion of the respondents are satisfied with the limitations of Automatic Teller Machines and some of the Automatic Teller Machines users are moderately satisfied with the limitations of ATM Card services. Only few respondents are dissatisfied with the limitations of Automatic Teller Machines.
6. From the above analysis it was found that challenges associated with Automated Teller Machines are waiting in queues at ATM centres, ATM machine out of service, out of cash and non- printing of transaction.
7. Most of the sample respondents are opened that need to establish more Automatic Teller Machines at rural areas with better functionality. Some of the Automatic Teller Machine users suggested enhanced security measures, need to reduced transaction fees and provide fast customer services.

CONCLUSION

Most of the Automated Teller Machine (ATM) users are facing challenges such as additional charges after limited withdrawals, while the remaining respondents reported issues like lack of ATMs in rural areas, out-of-service machines, difficulty in understanding ATM operations, and privacy-related concerns.

The study concludes that banks need to establish more ATMs in rural areas with better functionality, enhance security measures, reduce transaction fees, and provide faster customer services.

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